

1 **Tnf superfamily silencing in cervical cancer.**

2 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
3 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
4 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
5 East Islip, NY USA 11730

6 We measured total transcription by RNA-sequencing in an organoid cell culture system modeling
7 transformation in the cervix. We demonstrate here silencing of TNF superfamily members including
8 *Tnfrsf25* and *Tnfrsf14* during induction of transformation in the human cervix.

9 Citations

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